

Influence of manufacturing defects on the interlaminar shear strength of fibre-metal laminates

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Motivation – state of the art

Advantage of fibre-metal laminates (FML)

- High specific strength
- Very good fatigue properties
- Good impact properties

Limitations and challenges forming FML

- Low formability
- High manufacturing costs (autoclave process)
- Draping of fibres restricted

Process development is needed → deep drawing combined with resin transfer molding

Manufacturing process [1]

Materials

- Cold rolled pretreated steel DC04

- E-glass fibre-reinforced polymer (Elium 150)

Preparation of the sheets

- Cleaning
- Mech. & chem. treatment

Positioning

Injection and forming

Curing

Results of shear edge test [2]

Voids in volume

Surface voids

- Shear strength of specimens out of flat panels: 35 MPa
- Voids at surface ~1.4 %
→ Leading to premature failure

Conclusion

- No influence of fiber orientation on interlaminar shear strength → Superposition due to infiltration influence
- Influence on manufacturing process:
 - Void formation in the flange (premature failure)
 - Less favorable infiltration behavior toward the edge

Outlook

- Deeper analysis of manufacturing process
 - Influence of viscosity on drawability
 - Pressure profile all over the structure
- Optimization of process parameters
- Analysis of tempering on adhesion

- Mennecart, T., L. Hiegemann, and N.B. Khalifa, 2017. Analysis of the forming behaviour of in-situ drawn sandwich sheets. *Procedia Engineering*, 207, 890-895
- Roßmanith, P. 2018 Investigation of the influence of the process on the interlaminar shear strength of 3D curved fiber-metal-laminates. BA thesis, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology